

ECONOMIC ESSENCE AND INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT POLICY

Bobur Saidnazar o'g'li Mamataliyev
Tashkent State University of Economics. Uzbekistan

Abstract: In article problems of management are considered by investment projects. Management of investments are presented as system of principles and methods of development and realization of the administrative decisions connected with realization of various aspects of investment activity of the enterprise

Keywords: investments, investment activity, investment project, investment management, investment risks, system approach, management decisions, investments, investment activity, investment project, investment management, investment risks, system approach, management decision-making.

Investment activity is the activity of entities in the investment market, the purpose of which is to expand the economic potential of the investment object with the help of the most effective forms of capital investment within the framework of the overall development strategy. Investment activity in Uzbekistan began to develop actively in the era of the development of market relations. In the early 90s, almost all sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan came to a state of stagnation, due to the development of inflationary processes in the country. However, in the mid-90s, the situation changed for the better. At this time, new enterprises began to appear, existing ones were modernized, which required the active development of the investment market. At the beginning of the XXI century, the real investment market has become one of the most developing. At the moment, a large number of investment projects are being implemented in the country, the investors of which are foreign companies and private investors.

The urgency of the problem of investment project management is manifested due to the active development of the investment market in recent years. The effective activity of an enterprise in the long term, ensuring high rates of their development

and increasing competitiveness in the conditions of transition to a market economy is largely determined by the level of their investment activity and the range of investment activities.

Investment management is a system of principles and methods for the development and implementation of management decisions related to the implementation of various aspects of an enterprise's investment activity at the pre-investment, investment and post-investment stages. Investment management involves a number of problems that arise during the selection of alternative investment projects (pre-investment stage), their implementation (investment stage) and at the operational stage (post-investment stage).

At the pre-investment stage, the main problem of the enterprise is the search for an investor. All investment projects that are implemented at enterprises are financed from their own funds and from external sources. Finding investors is an urgent problem for all domestic enterprises and small businesses in general. Any enterprise for expansion of its activities, commissioning of new facilities, expansion or modernization resorts to financing from both internal and external sources. Financing from internal sources causes the diversion of the company's funds from circulation, which entails the occurrence of financial difficulties and, as a result, losses of the company in the form of losses. Financing from external sources can be divided into two types: fixing for attracting bank and credit and financing at the expense of investors. The use of a bank loan for an enterprise is an expensive source of raising funds, moreover, not all enterprises implementing an investment project meet the permissible and necessary class of creditworthiness. In addition, newly created enterprises that do not have delivery capital, guarantees and guarantees of repayment of the loan received may receive the funds necessary for the

implementation of investment projects for the implementation of an investment project is not enough.

At the investment stage, the actual problems in the implementation of investment projects are: very rapid growth of prices and tariffs, especially for construction materials; very high transport costs for the supply of equipment and materials; a long period of time for construction and installation of equipment, which increases the cost of the project; the likelihood of inaccurate calculations of the cost of the investment project due to the presence of inflation.

Investment activity is the activity of the subjects of the investment market, the purpose of which is to expand the economic potential of the object of investment with the help of the most effective forms of capital investment within the framework of the overall development strategy. Investment activity in Uzbekistan began to develop actively in the era of the development of market relations. In the early 90s, almost all sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan came to a state of stagnation, which is associated with the development of inflationary processes in the country. However, in the mid-90s, the situation changed for the better. At that time, new enterprises began to appear, existing ones were modernized, which required the active development of the investment market. At the beginning of the XXI century, the real investment market has become one of the most developing. Currently, a large number of investment projects are being implemented in the country, the investors of which are foreign companies and private investors.

The urgency of the problem of investment project management is manifested in connection with the active development of the investment market in recent years. The effective operation of an enterprise in the long term, ensuring high rates of its development and increasing competitiveness in the conditions of transition to a

market economy is largely determined by the level of its investment activity and the range of investment activities.

Investment management is a system of principles and methods for the development and implementation of management decisions related to the implementation of various aspects of an enterprise's investment activity at the pre-investment, investment and post-investment stages. Investment management involves a number of problems that arise when choosing alternative investment projects (pre-investment stage), their implementation (investment stage) and at the operational stage (post-investment stage).

At the pre-investment stage, the main problem of the enterprise is the search for an investor. All investment projects implemented at the enterprises are financed from their own funds and from external sources. The search for investors is an urgent problem for all domestic enterprises and small businesses in general. Any enterprise for expansion of its activities, commissioning of new facilities, expansion or modernization resorts to financing from both internal and external sources. Financing from internal sources causes the company's funds to be diverted from circulation, which entails financial difficulties and, as a result, the company's losses in the form of losses. Financing from external sources can be divided into two types: fixed for attracting bank and credit funds and financing at the expense of investors. The use of a bank loan for an enterprise is an expensive source of raising funds, moreover, not all enterprises implementing an investment project meet the acceptable and necessary creditworthiness class. In addition, newly created enterprises that do not have the supply capital, guarantees and guarantees of repayment of the loan received may receive the funds necessary for the implementation of investment projects, it is not enough to implement an investment project.

At the investment stage, the actual problems in the implementation of investment projects are: very rapid growth of prices and tariffs, especially for construction materials; very high transport costs for the supply of equipment and materials; a long period of time for the construction and installation of equipment, which increases the cost of the project; the likelihood of inaccurate calculations of the cost of the investment project due to the presence of inflation. The implementation of the main tasks of managing the investment activity of the enterprise is closely related to the functions of investment management. The following investment management functions are distinguished: - management of the formation of investment resources; - management of real investments; - management of financial investments; - management of investment cash flows [4].

The function of managing the formation of investment resources is to predict the total need for investment resources necessary for the implementation of the developed investment strategy at individual stages of its implementation. In the process of optimizing the structure of sources of investment resources, a rational ratio of attracted equity and borrowed capital is ensured. The function of managing real investments is revealed in the need for renovation of existing fixed assets and intangible assets, as well as in the volume and structure of newly formed capital assets; search and evaluation of investment attractiveness of individual real projects and selection of the most effective of them; formation of the investment program of real investments of the enterprise and ensuring its implementation. In the process of implementing the financial investment management function, investment objectives are determined; investment qualities of investment instruments are evaluated and the most effective of them are selected; a portfolio of financial investments is formed according to the criteria of its profitability, risk and liquidity. The function of managing investment cash flows provides forecasting of cash flows in the course of

investment activities, balancing their volumes, synchronizing cash flows over time. Each of these functions can be specified more purposefully, taking into account the specifics of the investment activity of the enterprise.

The management of real investments is a multifaceted and complex process that requires a systematic approach. The system approach is a methodology for considering various kinds of complexes, which allows deeper and better understanding of their essence (structure, organization) and finding optimal ways and methods of influencing the development of such complexes and their management system [4].

The systematic approach assumes a comprehensive account of the specific characteristics of the relevant object, which determine its structure, and therefore its organization.

Each system has its own inherent features, its response to management, its forms of possible deviation from the program, its ability to respond to various kinds of impacts. A systematic approach to the management of real investments involves considering such management as procedures or processes for making managerial decisions or risk decisions.

The process of making managerial decisions and risk decisions, in our opinion, includes the following stages:

- analysis of options;
- assessment of achievements and losses for each option;
- assessment of the actual results of implemented decisions.

The adoption of a management decision and the risk of a decision is preceded by an economic analysis aimed at exploring options. The criterion for making a decision is the choice of the most economic option. Increasing the role of economic

analysis in decision-making led to the use of system analysis, which was due to fundamental changes in the management of real investments, namely:

- the transition from current process management to strategic, promising;
- the transition from isolated private subsystems to complex systems; - increased flexibility and efficiency in the development of processes, markets;
- the transition from the analysis of individual cases to a systematic analysis of solutions;
- the transition from the calculation of individual elements of efficiency to a comprehensive one.

Investment activity is the activity of entities in the investment market, the purpose of which is to expand the economic potential of the investment object with the help of the most effective forms of capital investment within the framework of the overall development strategy. Investment activity enables enterprises to implement projects and improve their material and technical condition. The result of the implementation of real investment projects is an increase in output per worker, a reduction in cost, a reduction in costs, an increase in net income, an improvement in the quality of goods and products through the introduction of new equipment and technologies. The main problems in the implementation of investment projects are: rapid growth of prices and tariffs, high transportation costs.

References

1. Ivashkovsky S.N. Economics: micro and macroanalysis: textbook-practice. manual / S.N. Ivashkovsky. - M.: Delo, 1999. - 360 s
2. Yerkov, A. //Financial newspaper. Regional issue. - No. 38, September 2005.
3. Melkumov, Ya.S. Organization and financing of investments: studies. manual / Ya.S. Melkumov. - M.: INFRA-M, 2000– - 248s
4. Mizyun V.A. Economic assessment of investments: studies. manual / V.A. Mizyun. - Togliatti: Publishing House of TSU, 2006– - 138s.
5. Raximova, G., Abdullayev,A., Yusupova, M.. (2020)Buxgalteriya hisobi. Darslik.494.p.
6. Murodovna, R.G. Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets. International Journal of Financial Management and EconomicsInternational Journal of Financial Management and Economics 2021; 4(1): 41-45P-ISSN: 2617-9210, E-ISSN: 2617.
7. Rahimova G., (2021)Accounting of the results of continuous revaluation of property, plant and equipment in accordance with international standards. Society and innovations. Issue – 3 (2021) / ISSN 2181-1415 111-121 p.